

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Vaithilingam****FIRST NAME: Vinayagathas****PROGRAM CODE : DIDOL****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word on Mac

List your seven key concepts with the page number in-text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Research (EUCLID 2019, 2)
2. Literature Review (EUCLID 2019, 17-18)
3. Writing Style (EUCLID 2019, 24-25)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5)
5. Citation (EUCLID 2019, 6-7)
6. Paraphrasing (EUCLID 2019, 8)
7. Use of right vocabulary (EUCLID 2019, 27)

WRITING AN EFFECTIVE ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing is an essential skill to complete a doctoral program. I have gained those skills from my previous master's education. I have published a master thesis on "Impact of XML technologies for financial providers" and a conference paper in 2009. This research critically evaluates the different eXtensible Markup Language (XML) technologies for banking applications and services. Further, it discusses how XML supports for banking application security to unauthorized access and provides transactions to its customers.

Ten years later, I have decided to read a doctoral program and then joined a doctoral program at University. Following this course, ACA-401D - International Academic Writing (Doctorate) it allowed me to refresh my knowledge in academic writing and also will improve my research and academic writing skills.

Writing an academic essay consists of the necessary steps given in the ACA-401D course pack in chapter 1. In this response paper, my focus is given to the following concepts to make an effective essay.

2) RESEARCH

Academic writing is primarily based on research. Academic research is categorized as primary research and secondary research. The primary research can be conducted by interviews, surveys, questionnaires, observations, focus groups, and field visits, whereas secondary research can be involved in the data collection through already gathered, processed, organized, and published information by others.

A feature of most academic writing is that it draws on the work of other writers and researchers. Therefore, reading and researching are vital to essay writing. Researching provides the knowledge and evidence that allows you to develop a thesis and argument to answer the essay question (EUCLID 2019, 2).

Based on my academic and working experience, I learned and practiced academic writing and published a few research papers. Part of my teaching practices, I have recently done two action research papers that were based on my classroom. One of the research topics is, "How can hands-on lab practice increase student's comprehension of theoretical knowledge?" It was primary research. In the past, research was proven using various teaching methods, which increased students' understanding and engagement. However, in my action research, I studied that most of the students experienced and evidenced hands-on labs help them to practice what they being taught in lectures and allowed them to observe and understand what is happening directly. That is one of the best ways of learning by example, which benefits "Kinesthetic learners.

General guidelines (seventh point) for the essay is given in the material (EUCLID 2019, 4). Those guidelines are written specifically for the students from NSW university. I do not see anyone of the guidelines that match our EUCLID submission requirements.

3) LITERATURE REVIEW

In the ACA-401D course pack, chapter four starts with eleven important reminders to write an academic paper. The title of the chapter is misleading the learners. The ordinary meaning of the literature review is summarizing information or identifying the gap in the research.

A literature review surveys books, scholarly articles, and any other sources relevant to a particular issue, area of research, or theory. By so doing, it provides a description, summary, and critical evaluation of these works in relation to the research problem investigated. Literature reviews are designed to provide an overview of sources you have explored while researching a particular topic and to demonstrate to your readers how your research fits within a larger field of study (Labaree 2020, 1).

Followed by eleven important reminders, this chapter is described the grammar rules used in academic writing. Most of the rules are described as questions, and answers format like How many spaces go after a period? Or Can you begin a sentence with "and?" It is really helped to understand and apply easily in essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 22).

4) **WRITING STYLE**

Style can encompass many different aspects like referred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling (UK v US for example), readership considerations, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, the use of symbols, voice preferences (active v passive), structure, paragraph numbering and indentation, the use of headings, the use of lists and trademark or branding considerations (EUCLID 2019, 24–25).

Turabian is a simpler version of Chicago style meant for students who are writing materials that will not be published. The Turabian guide is shorter and includes information on formatting rules, the basics of researching and writing academic papers, and citation style. Since the Chicago Manual of Style (CMOS) is meant for material that is intended for publication, it is often used by scholars, publishers, and other professional academics (Hansen 2011).

I used Harvard style in one of my conference papers, titled as The Impact of XML technologies on Banking applications and services at the National Information Technology Conference (NITC) and also, in my master thesis. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) is another style, which is mostly used by students who write academic research papers in computer science or engineering. I have been reading technical papers in IEEE journals since 2012.

I am following the EUCLID recommendation as a writing style. EUCLID recommendation the Chicago Rules (Turabian), but other internationally recognized Rules are fine. EUCLID also recommends using American English, but both versions are obviously accepted (EUCLID 2019, 24).

5) **PLAGIARISM**

Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. When using any quote, paraphrase, statistic/data, or visuals (such as a graph) that is borrowed from another source (EUCLID 2019, 5)

There are 66% of 16,000 students from 31 prestigious US universities have cheated at least once, says 1991 Rutgers University study. 12% of those reported themselves as regular cheaters. This means nearly seven out of ten students cheat, and at least one of those cheats all the time! Cheating on campus increased an estimated 744% from 1993 to 1997, says the University of California-Berkley officials (CheckForPlagiarism.net n.d.).

A national survey published in Education Week found that 54% of students admitted to plagiarizing from the Internet; 74% of students admitted that at least once during the past school year they had engaged in "serious" cheating, and 47% of students believe their teachers sometimes choose to ignore students who are cheating (CheckForPlagiarism.net 2020).

The levels of misconduct described in the IEEE Guidelines (A Plagiarism FAQ n.d.):

1. Level One pertains to the uncredited verbatim copying of a full paper, or the verbatim copying of a major portion (> 50%), or verbatim copying within more than one paper by the same author(s).
2. Level Two pertains to the uncredited verbatim copying of a large portion (between 20-50%) or verbatim copying within more than one paper by the same author(s).
3. Level Three pertains to the uncredited verbatim copying of individual elements (paragraph(s), sentence(s), illustration(s), etc.), resulting in a significant portion (up to 20%) within a paper.
4. Level Four pertains to uncredited improper paraphrasing of pages or paragraphs.
5. Level Five pertains to the credited verbatim copying of a major portion of a paper without clear delineation (e.g., quotes or indents)

a) Citation

Plagiarism must be avoided in academic writing. In order to avoid plagiarism, the solution is to properly cite the author or source that has provided the information you are using (EUCLID 2019, 6). I used this textbook 'Cite them right The Essential referencing guide' for my master research, written by Richard Pears and Graham Shields.

A reference to an article plays a very vital role at the time of acceptance and also very helpful in finding out the origin of a study. Incomplete references, outdated references, and missing volume number, issue number, and year are always identified by the reviewers of journals. An accurate reference of a manuscript always considered as a principal issue and identifies the quality of the article. Some commercial software packages are now available in the market for managing citations, but most of them are unaffordable by a research scholar (Ray 2017, 238).

The ability to integrate with MS Word and OpenOffice make Zotero as ideal software. By using this facility, the users can simply insert in their personal library at the time of article composition (Ray 2017, 244).

b) Paraphrasing

Paraphrasing is one of the accepted approaches to use other authors' ideas and opinions in academic essay writing. It can be done using synonym words or changing sentences' part of speech or structure or converting sentence active voice to passive voice. Using quotations is one of the simple ways to use other ideas in our paper with a citation. Paraphrasing helps to avoid many quotations in an essay. It does not look very good if you have too many quotes. So, you will need to paraphrase at times (EUCLID 2019, 8).

LeBlanc from Fitchburg State University states that.

Quotes can help lend authority to an initial argument, but should not be relied upon too heavily in a paper. If you find yourself quoting an entire paragraph, a paraphrase or summary of that content may often be more appropriate (LeBlanc 2020, 1).

6) USE OF RIGHT VOCABULARY

The use of the right vocabulary will enhance academic writing. Students can strengthen their vocabulary by reading rich vocabulary books and also give attention to vocabulary while they read a book. If student want to improve the vocabulary with spelling, they should adopt one language pattern like American English or British English. Chapter six (6) of ACA-401D course pack, is well compared and contrast the linguistics nature of the US English language and UK English language and also the rules of both languages spelling and punctuation placement.

My previous academic works had been written in British English. Since 2014 I have been writing my academic communications and writings in Canadian English, which is closer to US English.

Canadian spelling of the English language combines British and American rules. Most notably, in Canada, French-derived words that in American English end with -or and -er, such as color or center, usually retain British spellings i.e., colour and centre. In other cases, Canadian and American spelling differs from British spelling in words such as realize and recognize, which in British English are spelled realise and recognise; i.e., usually spelled with -ize rather than -ise (Canadian_English.Pdf n.d.).

7) CONCLUSION

ACA-401D is not a core course for this doctoral program. However, it is a mandatory course for all the graduate programs with a research component and academic writing. Beginning graduate learning with this course will help the students to effectively write academic papers or essays in their fields of study.

I have learned how to use the Zotero software tool to collect, organize, and cite research and also used Grammarly software tool to eliminate errors in grammar and spelling. The course material is designed with the mistakes in sample quotations or papers that were intentionally not corrected in line, which really makes my learning interesting at the same time challenging too. This course satisfies the learning outcome and provides the necessary skills and knowledge to students in writing academic papers in an international context.

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